

**The European Energy Research Alliance (EERA)
Joint Programme on Nuclear Materials (JPNM)**

PILOT PROJECT PROPOSAL

Call 2021

Subprogramme: SP-A

Project proposal title:

Qualification and Design of Experiments for Structural Integrity of Materials in Pb and LBE

Project proposal acronym:

QUADESIM

Duration in months: 48

Main contact person (coordinator):

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Abstract:

To obtain a license to construct HLM cooled reactors, it must be demonstrated that the components will retain their structural integrity and functionality over their design life. Design/engineering data is based on comprehensive testing programs and evaluation and analysis by experts. Except probationary rules, currently, no nuclear design code includes rules regarding environmental effects from e.g. heavy liquid metals. The objective of this pilot project is to make a first step from research data towards design data by establishing a roadmap for generating data and to support their implementation into the RCC-MRx design code. This includes, for this project, data treatment, documentation and data storage. Only a very limited number of materials and properties will be selected to evaluate the process of moving from research to design data. Essential to an effective and efficient process are (1) a repository for the data, (2) a design-of-experiment and statistical evaluation and (3) an expert judgement on the completeness and quality of the data.

List of Participants:

Nr. *	Participant organisation full name	Short name	Country
1	SCK CEN	SCK CEN	Belgium
2	Bangor University	BU	Great Britain
3	CIEMAT	CIEMAT	Spain
4	CNRS	CNRS	France
5	CVR	CVR	Czech Republic
6	ENEA	ENEA	Italy
7	JRC - Petten	JRC	European Union
8	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology	KIT	Germany
9	NNL	NNL	Great Britain
10	Nuclear Research & Consultancy Group	NRG	Netherlands
11	RATEN	RATEN	Romania

*Participant Nr. 1 is the coordinator of the project, for the rest the order is alphabetical.

Effort and budget:¹

PARTICIPANT	PERSON-MONTHS*	PERSONNEL COSTS	OTHER COSTS	INDIRECT COSTS	TOTAL COSTS
BU	9 = 3 + 6				
CIEMAT	14 = 10 + 4	66304	5000	54248	125552
CNRS	5.5 = 3 + 2.5	36518	2500	9754	48772
CVR	12.5 = 6.5 + 6	43750	4000	11938	59688
ENEA	20 = 4 + 16	99558	20000	68506	188064
JRC	17 = 14 + 3	227230	5000	56807	289037
KIT	19 = 13 + 6	151050		37763	188813
NNL	4.5 = 4 + 0.5	50000	5000	10000	65000
NRG	5 = 3 + 2	53601	10640	35734	99975
RATEN	10 = 4 + 6	30000	10000	19000	59000
SCK CEN	18 = 15 + 3	185178	10000	129625	324803
TOTAL	129.5 = 79.5 + 55	943189	72140	433375	1448704

*WP4 contributions are maximum intentional. They depend on the extent and nature of the gaps to be filled. They are listed after the + sign.

¹ The costs given in this table should represent a **fair estimate of the real cost of the research proposed**, taking into account the cost of the personnel (including potential PhDs/post-docs if needed, see Section 2.1.) The information is needed to assign a correct value to the research proposed and each organization should be ready to bear the most part of it (in kind or from extra national funds), so that the project can start and partly progress. External sources of funding, if identified, will relieve the financial burden or allow the reach of the research to be extended further, within the same scope.

PARTICIPANT	IDENTIFICATION OF NATIONAL PROGRAMME
BU	BEIS sponsored AMR Phase 2; BEIS sponsored Advanced Fuel Cycle Programme
CIEMAT	
CNRS	
CVR	<i>Up to 20% (corrosion behaviour of uncoated T91 and 316L) may be covered by project No.: TK04030082 "Pretty Fast Flow" funded by the Technology Agency of the Czech Republic. The rest will be covered by the DKRVO programme of the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports.</i>
ENEA	
JRC	
KIT	Helmholtz Programme NUSAFE (100 %)
NNL	
NRG	
RATEN	Advanced Nuclear Reactors and Fuel Cycles
SCK CEN	Myrrha

Possible project reviewers:²

FIRST AND LAST NAME	AFFILIATION	E-MAIL ADDRESS
Cécile Petesch	CEA (France)	cecile.petesch@cea.fr
Janne Wallenius	KTH (Sweden)	janwal@kth.se
Pär Olsson	KTH (Sweden)	polsson@kth.se
?	Framatome (France)	
?	RCC-MRx	

² List 1-3 names of experts, not belonging to the JPNM and certainly not involved in the project, that could be good reviewers for your proposal.

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1. Research proposal

1.1 Background

Structural integrity qualification of materials is required when current materials are used in new applications or when new materials are used in current applications. Examples are the use of conventional stainless steel in heavy liquid metal or the use of additively manufactured stainless steel for any reactor type.

In order to demonstrate the structural integrity of material and components for structural applications one needs to evaluate their performance under the appropriate environmental conditions. Relevant properties need to be measured and assessed. Furthermore, the factors affecting material performance are specific for each material-environment combination. This leaves the materials engineer with a huge task in new situations. Working out the interacting effect of many factors on the behavioural properties of materials in a given environment is by no means trivial and a work of long duration and persistence.

The environmental effect of heavy liquid metals has not been included in the nuclear design codes such as RCC-MRx and ASME. As a first step the design Code RCC-MRx included, in its most recent version (2018), a guideline for using the code for HLM coolants. The guideline essentially states that an operator should ensure that the chosen material, in a chemistry controlled coolant, has the same behaviour as in air - except for the depletion of the corrosion allowance - and that all failure modes inside or outside of the design code shall be identified and addressed.

The development of design data and design rules to demonstrate this behaviour have been key items for recent EURATOM projects such as MATTER (2011-2015), MATISSE (2013-2017) and GEMMA (2017-2021). These projects have included both mechanical and corrosion tests, including development of test procedures, compilation of data in repositories and first design guidelines. Unfortunately, there is still a lack of full understanding and sometimes inconsistencies and, specific design data and rules are lacking. It is therefore very important to ensure that all data that have been generated are compiled and put in a form that allows analysis. Moreover, the complexity of interaction between HLM and structural materials require often expensive and long duration tests involving many factors. To get relevant data in support of design in a relative short time requires optimized test programmes.

In view of the current and international drive towards small modular reactors (SMRs), and the associated number of conceptual designs, contributions to a roadmap for qualifying materials in their environment in terms of structural integrity are becoming vital to the success of generation IV reactors and SMRs.

1.2 Objectives

The aim of the underlying pilot project proposal is to evaluate the way in which the use of design of experiment techniques and the consistent collection of properties in a repository can assist in the process of **acquiring relevant data in the shortest possible time**. Rating of dataset completeness and quality by materials experts **also** forms part of this evaluation. Based on this assessment complementary tests will be identified and if feasible conducted within the project. The set of data **looked at in this project** will be used **to draft** recommendations **and best practice guidelines** for **future** test programmes **that will** support material and component qualification.

The project aims to do this because many material-environment combinations will be used in generation IV reactors and SMRs. Although material performance might not immediately give rise to safety issues, and hence some aspects might not be addressed by the licensing authorities, the economics of inspection and replacement and its management might need to be considered by the vendors. Hence, a roadmap to adequately and effectively produce data for new material-environment combinations is a worthwhile quest.

1.3 Description of Work & Methodology

The pilot project is to work as much as possible with data from previous test programs and to only potentially address the acquisition of new data.

Hence, the pilot project consists of the following activities

- Review of design of experiments (DOE) approaches (by DOE expert) and first proposal for an optimized test programme based on DoE
- Identification of previous test programs that contain information related to material qualification (by stakeholders in the materials area)
- Identification of previous test programs that contain sufficient and appropriate information: data have to be available in a usable form, thus a repository for the data needs to exist and the data must be of relevance to designers (see Table 1 and Figure 1)
 - Selection of data from previous test programs that are or could still be entered in the data repository
 - Evaluation of the quality of the test matrix used in the selection using DOE (by DOE expert)
 - Evaluation of the completeness and quality of the test data in the selection (by material testing expert)
 - Evaluation of the dependencies present in the selection using statistical means (by material expert)
 - Review and potentially updating of data repository (MatDB);
 - Identification of gaps in the test matrix,
- Setting-up a complementary test programme.

These activities require the involvement of various experts in the areas of DOE, materials qualification, materials testing and statistical analysis.

There are several reasons why DOE and a repository are crucial to data qualification, as follows:

- Procurement of appropriate data requires extensive testing and comes at a high cost.
- DOE needs to identify gaps in the test matrix.
- DOE needs to identify issues with the test matrix.
- Data need to be safely stored for a long time.
- Data need to be stored in an easily recoverable form to avoid duplication in the future.
- Data need to be stored in a structured way to statistically assess effects.

Table 1

Data requirements	Data availability	Data repository
List required material properties for specific material-environment	Identify available property data for specific material-environment	Identify available property modules

Figure 1

1.4 Expected Main Results

1.4.1 Main result

- **Design-of-experiment guidelines** to effectively assist in the qualification of materials for use in structural applications.
- **Data repositories** and **expert evaluation** to effectively assist in the qualification of materials for use in structural applications.
- **Gap analysis** in terms of the qualification of the selected materials and properties for use in structural applications.
- **Standardization needs** in terms of the qualification of materials for use in structural applications.

1.4.2 Impact

Roadmap for material data qualification for structural integrity.

Future application of the roadmap to additional materials, environments and properties.

1.4.3 Risks

- Data release to the consortium might be subject to IPR.
- Data entry into a repository might be subject to IPR.
- Unable to identify an area with sufficient information (data-wise, repository-wise or requirement-wise).
- Reproducibility of experiments so far performed in HLM might be insufficient for useful parametric study.

1.5 Implementation

1.5.1 Work-package list and chart

WP Nr.	List of contributors (short names)	Short description of goals and expected results
1	BU,CIEMAT,CNRS,CVR,ENEA,JRC,KIT,NNL,NRG,SCKCEN	Identification of material property data for later analysis.
2	BU,CIEMAT,JRC,KIT,NNL,NRG,RATEN,SCKCEN	Analysis techniques (DOE and statistics).
3	BU,CIEMAT,CNRS,CVR,JRC,KIT,NNL,RATEN,SCKCEN	Analysis of selected property data.
4	BU,CIEMAT,CNRS,CVR,ENEA,JRC,KIT,NNL,NRG,RATEN,SCKCEN	Complementary test program.
5	BU,CIEMAT,CNRS,CVR,JRC,KIT,NNL,NRG,RATEN,SCKCEN	Recommendations & guidelines for the data qualification process.

1.5.2 Description of WPs

Work package number	WP1 (Tim Austin, JRC)	Start (project-month): 1	End (project-month): 18								
Work package title:	Identification of material property data for later analysis.										
Participants	BU	CIEMAT	CNRS	CVR	ENEA	JRC	KIT	NNL	NRG	SCK CEN	
Person-months per participant:	25.5	1	2	1	3	4	6	1.5	2	1	4
Objectives:											
TO identify material property data in past, present and future test programs in heavy liquid metal SO THAT the data can be analysed in WP3.											
Description of the work/task breakdown:											
<p><u>T1.1:</u> Data identification, gathering and screening</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identify previous test programs that contain information related to material qualification (by stakeholders in the materials area), including a survey of project partner existing data and availability (employing the Annex 1 template of the OECD/NEA EGLM Structural Materials Data Management Survey) Identify which previous test programs contain sufficient and appropriate information for material qualification (by materials expert) Data sharing arrangements with projects and organisations to allow the reuse of existing data Development of data protocols to identify the data fields of interest Data screening in view of qualification (by materials expert) Select data from previous test programs that are or could still be entered in the data repository (MatDB) Enter and/or update data in the repository (MatDB) <p><u>T1.2:</u> Review and potentially update the repository (MatDB) Permission will be sought from consortia (such as MATTER and GEMMA) to review and potentially update existing data collections. The review process will give attention to data completeness and quality.</p> <p><u>T1.3:</u> Establish the long term prospects of the repository (MatDB as database or software) This task will give attention to ensuring the existence of the repository over the longer term, such as by seeking a commitment from the JRC or by establishing a clearing house with a long term perspective.</p> <p>Note: Material property data have to be available, a repository for the data needs to exist and the material property must be of relevance to designers.</p>											
List of milestones:											
<u>M1.1:</u> Material data identified (month 12)											
<u>M1.2:</u> Repository ready (month 12)											
<u>M1.3:</u> Repository filled out with existing data (month 18)											
List of deliverables:											
<u>D1.1:</u> Description of the material repository (MatDB) used in the pilot project (month 12), Tim Austin (JRC)											
<u>D1.2:</u> Material properties and data of the pilot project (month 18) , Tim Austin (JRC)											

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Work package number	WP2 (Daniele Baraldi, JRC)	Start (project-month): 1	End (project-month): 24
Work package title:	Analysis techniques (DOE and statistics).		
Participants	BU	CIEMAT	JRC
		KIT	NNL
		RATEN	SCK CEN
Person-months per participant:	10.5	1	2
	1	2	3
	1	1	0.5
	1	2	1
Objectives:			
TO review design of experiment approaches and statistical techniques SO THAT they can be used for data analysis in WP3.			
Description of the work/task breakdown:			
<u>T2.1:</u> Design of experiment <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Review of design-of-experiments (DOE) approaches (e.g. full factorial design, fractional factorial design, and response surface design). Both the methods for the experiments planning and the related methods of analysis of the experimental data will be reviewed. The review will identify the pros and cons of the different DOE approaches with to select a suitable DOE approach for the available experimental data in T3.1. 			
<u>T2.2:</u> Review of statistical techniques used for the evaluation of material property data. This task will review existing statistical techniques for data analysis which are not included in the DOE approaches.			
List of milestones:			
<u>M2.1:</u> DOE approaches reviewed (month 12)			
<u>M2.2:</u> Statistical techniques for material data evaluation reviewed (month 18)			
List of deliverables:			
<u>D2.1:</u> List and assessment of reviewed DOE approaches and statistical techniques with an indication of preference (month 24) , Daniele Baraldi (JRC)			

Work package number	WP3 (Marc Vankeerberghen, sck cen)		Start (project-month): 12	End (project-month): 45							
Work package title:	Analysis of selected property data.										
Participants		BU	CIEMAT	CNRS	CVR	JRC	KIT	NNL	NRG	RATEN	SCK CEN
Person-months per participant:	27.5	0.5	4	1.5	3	4	5.5	1	1	2	5
Objectives:											
TO evaluate gathered material property data in terms of readiness for material qualification SO THAT a recommendation for the future qualification of material properties can be made (WP5).											
Description of the work/task breakdown:											
<p><u>T3.1:</u> DOE-evaluation of data identified in WP1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preliminary evaluation in anticipation of the selection of preferred DOE techniques (by DOE expert) Here we will, whilst WP1 data gathering and WP2 selection of DOE techniques are still ongoing, already try to evaluate test matrices of historical test programs. • Evaluate the quality of the test matrix used in the selected data using preferred DOE (by DOE expert) Here we will evaluate the test matrices of the selected properties and datasets (WP1 outcome) with the preferred DOE and analysis techniques (WP2 outcome). <p><u>T3.2:</u> Evaluate the completeness and quality for each dataset in the selection (by material testing expert) In this task we will evaluate the completeness of the metadata associated with each dataset and also rate the quality of each dataset. The rules/criteria for the rating will first be jointly agreed upon between the partners.</p> <p><u>T3.3:</u> Evaluate the dependencies in available data using statistical means (by material expert) In this task we will analyse the selected datasets to identify trends in the dependency of properties (dependent variables) on independent variables and to determine the statistical significance thereof.</p> <p><u>T3.4:</u> Identify gaps in the test matrix and, if needed, set-up a test programme to address them Whilst we are evaluating the test matrices with DOE techniques and the results using statistical techniques it might become apparent that further testing would be needed in order to improve upon the test matrix and the evaluation of trends. To fill the identified gaps a complimentary test program will be defined.</p>											
List of milestones:											
<p><u>M3.1:</u> Preferred DOE and statistical analysis applied (month 24)</p> <p><u>M3.2:</u> Gap assessment 1: Suggestion for complementary testing (month 24)</p> <p><u>M3.3:</u> Completeness and quality rating given (month 24)</p> <p><u>M3.4:</u> Dependencies evaluated (month 36)</p> <p><u>M3.5:</u> Gaps assessment 2: Future test programmes (month 36)</p>											
List of deliverables:											
<u>D3.1:</u> Evaluation of the readiness of the selected data sets and associated material properties for inclusion in a design code (month 45), Marc Vankeerberghen (sck cen)											

Work package number	WP4* (Lukas Kosek, CVR)	Start (project-month): 24	End (project-month): 42									
Work package title:	Complementary test programme.											
Participants	BU	CIEMAT	CNRS	CVR	ENEA	JRC	KIT	NNL	NRG	RATEN	SCK CEN	
Person-months per participant:	55	6 +PhD	4	2.5	6	16	3	6	0.5	2	6 +1PhD	3
Objectives:												
To generate additional material property data SO THAT identified gaps in property data can be filled.												
Description of the work/task breakdown:												
The work depends on the properties identified at the start of the project and the fort gap analysis. In case partners have planned tests that can be adjusted to the needs of the project, then the testing can start earlier.												
<u>T4.1:</u> Generation of additional material property data to address identified gaps through additional tests - Mechanical tests.												
<u>T4.2:</u> Generation of additional material property data to address identified gaps through additional tests - Corrosion tests.												
Note: By necessity new testing based on the gaps (M3.2) is restricted to tests that can be prepared and carried out within two years.												
List of milestones:												
<u>M4.1:</u> Complementary test data generated (month 36)												
<u>M4.2:</u> Complementary test data rated (month 42)												
List of deliverables:												
<u>D4.1:</u> Complementary material property data included in the data base (month 36) , Lukas Kosek (CVR)												

*WP4 contributions are maximum intentional. They depend on the extent and nature of the gaps to be filled.

Work package number	WP5 (Carsten Schroer, KIT)		Start (project-month): 36	End (project-month): 48							
Work package title:	Recommendations & guidelines for the data qualification process.										
Participants		BU	CIEMAT	CNRS	CVR	JRC	KIT	NNL	NRG	RATEN	SCK CEN
Person-months per participant:	16	0.5	2	0.5	0.5	1	5	0.5	1	1	4
Objectives:											
<p>TO make recommendations and draft guidelines for material property programs in view of material qualification for structural application SO THAT an efficient creation of a comprehensive data handbook is enabled.</p>											
Description of the work/task breakdown:											
<p>T5.1: Draft lessons learned from current programs on material property harvesting in terms of readiness for use of the material properties in a design code.</p> <p>Through the process of mining, rating, evaluating the selected material properties it will become clear whether or not the practises followed in previous test programs are adequate to support the incorporation of the selected properties in a design code. In case the practices need to be improved, suggestions will be made and, if possible, already implemented in the current pilot project. Simultaneously, if any gaps in the body of data related to the selected properties have been identified based on DOE and statistical techniques, suggestions as to preferred DOE and statistical techniques will be made and, if feasible, already appended in the current pilot project. Furthermore, if shortcomings in the current repository are identified, recommended improvements will be suggested and, if feasible, already implemented during the current pilot project.</p> <p>T5.2: Engage with ISO/TC 156 (Corrosion of metals and alloys) on the topic of promoting the MATTER testing protocols to normative status.</p> <p>Repositories related to material properties store data in a systematic way and, preferably, according to an international standard related to testing for the material property. In respect of testing in an environment these standards often do not exist and efforts will be made to promote working towards them.</p>											
List of milestones:											
M5.1: Recommendations drafted (month 42)											
List of deliverables:											
D5.1: Recommendations and guidelines for the process of data qualification for structural applications in heavy liquid metal (month 48), Carsten Schroer (KIT)											
D5.2: Closing workshop, presentations (month 48), Carsten Schroer (KIT)											

2. Consortium description

2.1 Consortium as a whole

The consortium includes 10 organizations that all have been involved in testing, designing or developing of assessment procedures for nuclear components in heavy liquid metals. Most of the partners have been directly involved in the recent EURATOM projects MATTER, MATISSE and GEMMA. Most of the project partners are national research laboratories with strong links to the nuclear industry. To ensure the industrial relevance of the work, the consortium intends to establish formal links with industrial partners, code development and standardization organizations.

STAFF INVOLVED*	TOTAL NUMBER	PERSON MONTHS
Staff researchers	~32	~70%
Post-docs / Early-stage researchers*		
PhD students*	~5	~10%
Technicians	~12	~20%

*Need to be already identified or planned within national funding schemes

2.2 Participants

Note: Listing in alphabetical order.

2.2.1 Bangor University (UK)

Project contributions to WP1 (T1.1), WP2 (T2.1), WP3, WP4 (T4.1), WP5.

2.2.1.1 Short description of the participating organisation

Bangor University set up the Nuclear Futures Institute in 2017 to support nuclear new-build and training in the North Wales region and to support the wider UK programme. The university has a long history of world-leading research for energy systems after opening in 1884. Since its inception in late 2017 – the Nuclear Futures Institute has built fabulous facilities that are being used by leading industry stakeholders to aid nuclear technology development. We are ready and open for business. This includes the Bangor University Lead Loop for Erosion/corrosion Testing (BULLET) facility, sponsored by the BEIS Advanced Modular Reactor Programme – Phase 2, through Westinghouse Electric, and the BEIS sponsored Advanced Fuel Cycle Programme. In addition to BULLET, the Nuclear Futures Institute oversees a range of modelling and experimental facilities, including those that are able to handle uranium for fuel research. The Nuclear Futures Institute has activities in advanced reactors, fuels, fuel performance, thermal hydraulics, reactor physics, regulation, medicine, control and instrumentation and fusion energy.

2.2.1.2 Staff involved

STAFF INVOLVED*	EXPERTISE/TASK	PERSON MONTHS
<i>Simon Middleburgh</i>	<i>Experimental support and mechanistic modelling</i>	5
<i>Alberto Fraile</i>	<i>Modelling and experimental support for BULLET</i>	4
<i>PhD</i>	<i>Corrosion testing</i>	3

*The first column should contain the name (preferred) or the qualification (e.g. technician). Indicate on this table if you expect to be able to recruit a PhD student or a post-doc.

2.2.1.3 Facilities used

NAME and/or CATEGORY*	USE IN THE PROJECT
<i>BULLET (Erosion-corrosion Test Facility, Pb-loop)</i>	<i>Erosion/Corrosion in HLM</i>

*If the facility has a name, write it; in any case provide short description of it (e.g., Pb loop, hot cell lab, ion accelerator, ...)

2.2.2 CIEMAT (E)

Project contributions to WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5.

2.2.2.1 Short description of the participating organisation

CIEMAT (Centro de Investigaciones Energéticas, Medioambientales y Tecnológicas) is a public research body assigned to the Ministry of Science, Innovation and Universities, focused on energy and environment, and the technologies related to them. The Materials for Energy Interest Division at the Technology Department aims to understand and predict degradation mechanisms under extreme conditions on materials for energy production including nuclear and renewables energies. The division is strongly involved in several international (IAEA, NEA, EPRI, EU) and national projects (Spanish utilities, national research programs) on the material issues for decades. In particular, the division contribute to EC funded projects since the 4th FWP, having participated in different research projects such as CASTOC, TECLA, SPIRE, EUROTRANS-DEMETERA, LIRES, PERFECT; HELIMNET, PERFORM, GETMAT, LONGLIFE, SOTERIA, ATLAS+, GEMMA, M4F (coordinator), MEACTOS (coordinator), ENTENTE (coordinator).

2.2.2.2 Staff involved

STAFF INVOLVED*	EXPERTISE/TASK	PERSON MONTHS
<i>Marta Serrano</i>	<i>Guidelines and standardization</i>	<i>4</i>
<i>Rebeca Hernandez</i>	<i>Testing and analysis</i>	<i>6</i>
<i>Antonio Fernandez-Viña Reinoso</i>	<i>Testing and analysis</i>	<i>4</i>

*The first column should contain the name (preferred) or the qualification (e.g. technician). Indicate on this table if you expect to be able to recruit a PhD student or a post-doc.

2.2.2.3 Facilities used

NAME and/or CATEGORY*	USE IN THE PROJECT
<i>Liquid metal embrittlement laboratory</i>	<i>Creep and SSRT in liquid metals</i>
<i>Microscopy and surface analysis laboratory</i>	<i>SEM, OM</i>

*If the facility has a name, write it; in any case provide short description of it (e.g., Pb loop, hot cell lab, ion accelerator, ...)

2.2.3 CNRS-UMET (F)

Project contributions to WP1, WP3, WP4, WP5.

2.2.3.1 Short description of the participating organisation

The CNRS (National Centre for Scientific Research) is a government-funded research organisation under the administrative authority of the French Ministry in charge of research. As the largest fundamental research organisation in Europe, CNRS is organised in more than 1100 research units spread throughout France. These units are either intramural or in partnership with universities, other research organisations, or industry.

The CNRS, acting on behalf and for the Université of Lille, Centrale Lille Institut and INRAE in the framework of the joint research unit UMET (UMR8207) led by Patrice WOISEL.

The UMET – UMR8207 (Unité Matériaux Et Transformations) laboratory is a joint research unit between CNRS, Université de Lille, Centrale Lille Institut and INRAE. It aims at focusing research activity on materials inside the Chevreul Fédération of University of Lille. UMET laboratory is directed by Prof. Patrice WOISEL, is a total of 110 permanent persons and comprises six teams: therapeutic and molecular materials, physical metallurgy and materials engineering, minerals physics, plasticity, polymer engineering and interface processes and hygiene of materials. The team “physical metallurgy and materials engineering” is strongly involved in the study of materials for nuclear applications. They have strong expertise as well in the field of liquid metal assisted damage of structural alloys) as in the field of neutron irradiation degradation studied by simulation. The team has been involved in European projects for a long time (from FP4 to FP7 and H2020 and HORIZON2020) such as TECLA, MEGAPIE-Test, DEMETRA, GETMAT, PERFORM60, MATISSE, GEMMA, ENTENTE, INNUMAT.

2.2.3.2 Staff involved

STAFF INVOLVED*	EXPERTISE/TASK	PERSON MONTHS
<i>Ingrid Proriot Serre</i>	<i>Mechanical and damage of metallic materials in presence of liquid metal</i>	<i>2.5</i>
<i>Jocelyn Golek</i>	<i>Mechanical testing in liquid metal</i>	<i>2</i>
<i>Damien Creton</i>	<i>Metallurgical preparation</i>	<i>1</i>

*The first column should contain the name (preferred) or the qualification (e.g. technician). Indicate on this table if you expect to be able to recruit a PhD student or a post-doc.

2.2.3.3 Facilities used

NAME and/or CATEGORY*	USE IN THE PROJECT
<i>Mechanical tests in liquid metal lab</i>	<i>Mechanical test (monotone) in liquid Pb or LBE</i>
<i>SEM-EDX</i>	<i>Fracture surface observation</i>

*If the facility has a name, write it; in any case provide short description of it (e.g., Pb loop, hot cell lab, ion accelerator, ...)

2.2.4 CVR (CZ) - Centrum vyzkumu Rez s.r.o. - <http://cvrez.cz/en/>

Project contributions to WP1 (T1.1, T1.2), WP2 (T2.1), WP4 (T4.1), WP5 (T5.1).

Project management: WP4 leader.

2.2.4.1 Short description of the participating organisation

Research organization Centrum vyzkumu Rez (CVR), UJV Group Member, was established in 2002 as a daughter company of UJV Rez. Its principal mission is to perform applied R&D in energy and neutron physics as well as act as Czech Technical Safety Organization (TSO). Two research reactors and a set of experimental equipment (probes and loops) form the backbone of the research infrastructure of the company. This makes CVR able to participate in sophisticated research projects and participate in the development of new technologies for GEN IV and the fusion reactor. CVR participates in Jules Horowitz Reactor Project (hot laboratories development and supply), coordinated the CP FP7 SCWR-Fuel Qualification Test project, and implemented a large ERDF project “Sustainable Energy” (SUSEN). CVR represents the Czech Republic in the Executive Committee of the European Energy Research Alliance. CVR has significant experience in reactor R&D as well as in project management.

2.2.4.2 Staff involved

STAFF INVOLVED*	EXPERTISE/TASK	PERSON MONTHS
Michal CHOCHOLOUSEK	Mechanical testing	4.5
Lukas KOSEK	Corrosion expositions	4
R&D expert	Data analysis	2

*The first column should contain the name (preferred) or the qualification (e.g. technician). Indicate on this table if you expect to be able to recruit a PhD student or a post-doc.

2.2.4.3 Facilities used

NAME and/or CATEGORY*	USE IN THE PROJECT
Pb facility	Electromechanical tensile/compression testing machine with Pb/LBE testing cell for SSRT/FT/fatigue, with oxygen concentration regulation and control.
MATLOO	Non-isothermal corrosion lead loop with an active oxygen control system, parallel corrosion test sections with a maximum temperature of 520°C, and flow velocity up to 3m/s.

*If the facility has a name, write it; in any case provide short description of it (e.g., Pb loop, hot cell lab, ion accelerator, ...)

2.2.5 ENEA (I)

Project contributions to WP1, WP4.

2.2.5.1 Short description of the participating organisation

ENEA is a national research organization whose main activity is the development of new technologies in the fields of energy and sustainable economic development. Its two fundamental tasks are to conduct research in these areas and to diffuse the results nationally.

It is the leading Italian research institution in the R&D for nuclear fusion and Generation IV nuclear fission Fast Reactors (FR) and Accelerators Driven Systems (ADS) cooled by Heavy Liquid Metals (HLM). The Department of Fusion and Technologies for Nuclear Safety and Security (FSN) is composed of several laboratories which are equipped with experimental devices and facilities to perform research activities researches for the development of HLM technology and materials to be used in contact with lead, lead-bismuth and lead-lithium alloys.

ENEA is a member of the European Sustainable Nuclear Energy Technology Platform (SNETP), the European Energy Research Alliance (EERA) and the Joint Programme on Nuclear Materials (JPNM). It is a founder member of the FALCON consortium, led by Ansaldo Nucleare (ANN), whose mission is the implementation of the LFR demonstrator ALFRED, one of the four demonstrators proposed by ESNII (European Sustainable Nuclear Industrial Initiative) in Europe for the demonstration of the Generation IV Fast Neutron Reactor technologies.

The staff is composed of more than 2000 employees, out of which most of them are engaged in R&D activities operating in 9 major research centres spread in Italy.

2.2.5.2 Staff involved

STAFF INVOLVED*	EXPERTISE/TASK	PERSON MONTHS
Carlo Cristalli	Researcher; Mechanical testing	3
Serena Bassini	Researcher; Corrosion	1
Camillo Sartorio	Researcher; Data analysis and management	2
Massimo Angiolini	Researcher; microstructural investigations	2
Nicola Bettocchi	Technician; Mechanical testing	6
Luigi Masotti	Technician; Mechanical testing	6

*The first column should contain the name (preferred) or the qualification (e.g. technician). Indicate on this table if you expect to be able to recruit a PhD student or a post-doc.

2.2.5.3 Facilities used

NAME and/or CATEGORY*	USE IN THE PROJECT
Hydraulic tensile testing machine with Pb testing cell for SSRT, with oxygen concentration regulation and control.	SSRT tests
Microscopy and surface analysis laboratory (SEM)	Investigation of fracture surfaces and corrosion thickness

*If the facility has a name, write it; in any case provide short description of it (e.g., Pb loop, hot cell lab, ion accelerator, ...)

2.2.6 JRC (NL)

Project contributions to WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4 and WP5.

Project management: WP1 & WP2 leader.

JRC will contribute to all Work Packages. A key contribution is supporting the other partners in management and analysis of data and in particular MatDB, developed by JRC. JRC will also provide general knowledge in design codes and test standards and methodologies for the Design of Experiments. JRC will also conduct a limited test programme in WP4 based on our feasibility and recommendations from WP3. JRC will lead WP1 & WP2.

2.2.6.1 Short description of the participating organisation

The Joint Research Centre (JRC) is European Commission's in-house science service comprising seven research Institutes located in five EU Member States (Belgium, Germany, Italy, the Netherlands, and Spain). The Directorate G Nuclear Safety and Security and the unit G.I.4 Nuclear Reactor Safety and Emergency Preparedness provides scientific and technical support for the conception, development, implementation, and monitoring of community policies related to energy and transport. For this purpose, JRC-G carries out analytical and experimental R&D on nuclear safety with respect to reactor safety, fuel-cycles and waste management. The unit G.I.4 assesses the integrity of nuclear components exposed to harsh environments and develops related methodologies, in support of the development of joint European design rules and standards. JRC is one of the founding members of EERA JPNM and sub-programme A Pre-normative research on materials and component qualification and data management.

2.2.6.2 Staff involved

STAFF INVOLVED*	EXPERTISE/TASK	PERSON MONTHS
<i>Karl-Fredrik Nilsson</i>	<i>Senior expert: Code & standards</i>	3
<i>Daniele Baraldi</i>	<i>Scientist: Design of Experiments</i>	5
<i>Tim Austin</i>	<i>Scientist: Data management expert, ISO Liaison Officer</i>	6
Peter Hähner	Senior expert: Material physics and testing	2
Technician		1

*The first column should contain the name (preferred) or the qualification (e.g. technician). Indicate on this table if you expect to be able to recruit a PhD student or a post-doc.

2.2.6.3 Facilities used

NAME and/or CATEGORY*	USE IN THE PROJECT
MatDB (engineering materials data base)	WP 1-5
Liquid Lead Laboratory (LILLA)	Mechanical Tests in HLM (WP4)

*If the facility has a name, write it; in any case provide short description of it (e.g., Pb loop, hot cell lab, ion accelerator, ...)

2.2.7 KIT (D)

Project contributions to WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5.

Project management: WP5 leader.

2.2.7.1 Short description of the participating organisation

Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT) is a higher education and research organisation with about 9500 employees, 25,000 students, and a total annual budget of about 840 million Euro. It bundles the missions of a university of the state of Baden-Wuerttemberg and of a large-scale research institution of the Helmholtz Association. KIT's research programme Nuclear Waste Management, Safety and Radiation Research (NUSAFE) has a long tradition, is widely recognized and represents an integral part of national provident research, addressing the new challenges by providing core competences on the internationally highest level of science and technology regarding nuclear safety and waste management research. The contributing KIT institutes are the Institute for Pulsed Power and Microwave Technology (IHM) and the Institute of Applied Materials, with its units Mechanics of Materials and Interfaces (IAM-MMI) and Applied Material Physics (IAM-AWP). The respective working groups have expertise in the production and characterization of advanced materials for nuclear energy applications. They have been contributing to the European and worldwide research in this field over several decades, with a focus on the thermomechanical performance of materials and components as well as compatibility with liquid metals.

2.2.7.2 Staff involved

STAFF INVOLVED*	EXPERTISE/TASK	PERSON MONTHS
<i>Dr. Alfons Weisenburger</i>	<i>Advanced materials production , material compatibility with liquid metals, material characterization, experimental design</i>	6
<i>Dr. Jarir Aktaa</i>	<i>Mechanics of materials, constitutive modelling, structural analysis, design rules development</i>	2
<i>Dr. Carsten Schroer</i>	<i>Interaction of solid and liquid metals. Methods of controlling non-metals dissolved in liquid metals. Post-test examination, determination of mechanisms and kinetics.</i>	5
<i>Dr. Annette Heinzl</i>	<i>Materials compatibility with liquid metals, microstructure characterization techniques</i>	6

*The first column should contain the name (preferred) or the qualification (e.g. technician). Indicate on this table if you expect to be able to recruit a PhD student or a post-doc.

2.2.7.3 Facilities used

NAME and/or CATEGORY*	USE IN THE PROJECT
<i>COSTA (stagnant corrosion tests in HLM)</i>	<i>Corrosion in stagnant liquid metals</i>
<i>Frethme /fretting-corrosion in HLM</i>	<i>Fretting tests in HLM</i>
<i>Corella /erosion-corrosion in HLM</i>	<i>Erosion/corrosion in HLM</i>
<i>XRD/SEM/EDX/tensile, bending tests</i>	<i>Post-test evaluation</i>

*If the facility has a name, write it; in any case provide short description of it (e.g., Pb loop, hot cell lab, ion accelerator, ...)

2.2.8 NNL (GB)

Project contributions to WP1 (T1.1, T1.3), WP2 (T2.2), WP3, WP4 (T4.1), WP5.

2.2.8.1 Short description of the participating organisation

The NNL (National Nuclear Laboratory) is the UK governments fission research organisation employing circa 1300 employees. It operates £1.5 billion worth of unique nuclear facilities as well as non-active research facilities across the UK that support impactful research across the entire nuclear life cycle. NNL is strongly involved in several international (IAEA, NEA, EU GIF) and domestic projects (UK utilities and national research programmes). A recent resurgence in nuclear, in support of a drive to net zero and energy security has led to the investment in an “Advanced Fuel Cycle Programme” that has set to re-establish and, in some instances, develop UK capabilities and facilities that include liquid metal testing and manufacture of advanced materials for use in heavy liquid metals.

2.2.8.2 Staff involved

STAFF INVOLVED*	EXPERTISE/TASK	PERSON MONTHS
<i>Dr. Nicholas Barron</i>	<i>Fast Reactors and Fuel Materials</i>	<i>1</i>
<i>Dr. Susan Ortner</i>	<i>Materials Science Expert</i>	<i>1</i>
<i>Dr. Hannah Wilcox</i>	<i>Materials Scientist</i>	<i>2.5</i>

*The first column should contain the name (preferred) or the qualification (e.g. technician). Indicate on this table if you expect to be able to recruit a PhD student or a post-doc.

2.2.8.3 Facilities used

NAME and/or CATEGORY*	USE IN THE PROJECT
<i>BULLET (Bangor University Liquid Lead Erosion-corrosion Test) Facility (Pb-loop)</i>	<i>Erosion/corrosion in HLM</i>
<i>XRD/SEM/EDX/tensile, bending tests</i>	<i>Post-test evaluation</i>

*If the facility has a name, write it; in any case provide short description of it (e.g., Pb loop, hot cell lab, ion accelerator, ...)

2.2.9 Nuclear Research & Consultancy Group – NRG (NL)

Project contributions to WP1, WP3, WP4 and WP5.

2.2.9.1 Short description of the participating organisation

The Nuclear Research & Consultancy Group (NRG) is the nuclear centre of competence in the Netherlands. It was established in 1988. NRG is an internationally operating company with a staff of more than 500 persons who develop knowledge, processes and products for safe applications of nuclear technology in energy, environment and health. It also includes products, services and technologies for the safe and economic operation of existing nuclear power plants and future sustainable nuclear energy systems.

NRG has a complete set of nuclear facilities, in particular a 45 MW research reactor (HFR), hot cell laboratories and other laboratories for research and analyses (<https://www.nrg.eu/>).

2.2.9.2 Staff involved

STAFF INVOLVED*	EXPERTISE/TASK	PERSON MONTHS
Fitriana Nindiyasari	Lead scientist	2
Romy Welschen	Lead scientist	1
Theo Baker	Mechanical property operator	1
Sander Hageman	Microscopist	1

*The first column should contain the name (preferred) or the qualification (e.g. technician). Indicate on this table if you expect to be able to recruit a PhD student or a post-doc.

2.2.9.3 Facilities used

NAME and/or CATEGORY*	USE IN THE PROJECT
Mechanical tests - Reference labs.	Mechanical test in air at RT & high temperature
Microscope(s)	Microstructure analysis

*If the facility has a name, write it; in any case provide short description of it (e.g., Pb loop, hot cell lab, ion accelerator, ...)

2.2.10 RATEN (Ro)

Project contributions to WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5.

2.2.10.1 Short description of the participating organisation

Regia Autonoma Tehnologii pentru Energia Nucleara (RATEN ICN) is a strategic Romanian Legal Entity coordinating the R&D activity in the nuclear energy field, which maintains and develops the scientific and technological support for the National Nuclear Energy Program. The Institute for Nuclear Research, RATEN subsidiary, is a complex R&D centre with over 40 years of activity in the nuclear energy field, deeply involved in the management and execution of the R&D National Nuclear Power Program. The main activities cover a large spectrum of nuclear energy: nuclear safety, designing, manufacturing and testing of nuclear fuels, ageing mechanisms of structural materials, irradiation technologies and radioisotopes production in the TRIGA 14MW research reactor, fuel and material irradiation tests, instrumentation and control, environmental protection, and radioactive waste management. The Institute owns a large experimental infrastructure, in front of the TRIGA reactors (the 14 MW steady-state core, and the ACPR pulsed core) and the hot cell facilities. RATEN is a member of the European Sustainable Nuclear Energy Technology Platform (SNETP) and the European Energy Research Alliance (EERA) and the Joint Programme on Nuclear Materials (JPNM). Also, it is a member of the FALCON consortium, whose mission is the implementation of the LFR demonstrator ALFRED, one of the four demonstrators proposed by ESNII (European Sustainable Nuclear Industrial Initiative) in Europe for the demonstration of the Generation IV Fast Neutron Reactor technologies. RATEN contributed to FP6 and FP7 projects (NULIFE, MATTER, STYLE, MatISSE, GEMMA, PATRICIA), and Coordinated Research Projects managed by IAEA-Vienna. The Institute is actively participating in the European Nuclear R&D, through memberships and participation in SNETP, NUGENIA and ESNII.

2.2.10.2 Staff involved

STAFF INVOLVED*	EXPERTISE/TASK	PERSON MONTHS
<i>Dr. Vasile RADU</i>	<i>Experience in theoretical and experimental investigation of components of NPP, Fitness-for-Service Assessment Methodology</i>	<i>1</i>
<i>Dr. Alexandru NITU</i>	<i>Nuclear material testing and device development</i>	<i>2</i>
<i>Dr. Livia STOICA</i>	<i>Microstructural and SEM analyses</i>	<i>2</i>
<i>Dr. Ionescu VIOREL</i>	<i>Nuclear material testing</i>	<i>1</i>
<i>Alexandra JINGA (PhD)</i>	<i>Nuclear material testing and microstructural analyses</i>	
<i>Marius CONSTANTINESCU</i>	<i>Manage the experimental testing facilities</i>	<i>4</i>

*The first column should contain the name (preferred) or the qualification (e.g. technician). Indicate on this table if you expect to be able to recruit a PhD student or a post-doc.

2.2.10.3 Facilities used

NAME and/or CATEGORY*	USE IN THE PROJECT
<i>LILETIN testing facility</i>	<i>Experimental tensile and fracture mechanics tests in the stagnant lead</i>
<i>Mechanical testing laboratory (Instron, Walter+Bai)</i>	<i>Mechanical testing in the air and stagnant lead</i>
<i>Metallographic laboratory</i>	<i>Microstructural and SEM characterization</i>

*If the facility has a name, write it; in any case provide short description of it (e.g., Pb loop, hot cell lab, ion accelerator, ...)

2.2.11 SCK CEN (B) – Studiecentrum voor Kernenergie – www.sckcen.be

Project contributions to WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4 and WP5.

Project management: Coordinator and WP3 leader.

2.2.11.1 Short description of the participating organisation

The Belgian Nuclear Research Centre, SCK•CEN, was founded in 1952 as a foundation of public utility with legal status according to private law, under the tutorial of the Belgian Federal Minister of Energy. The SCK•CEN statutory mission gives priority to research on issues of great societal concern, such as the safety and efficiency of nuclear installations; protection of mankind and environment from ionising radiation; production of radioisotopes for the medical sector; decommissioning, safe treatment and disposal of radioactive waste; non-proliferation of fissile materials; **development of innovative nuclear systems, e.g., the irradiation facility MYRRHA**; and education and training. To accomplish its mission, SCK•CEN operates several irradiation facilities, amongst which the BR2 reactor and ‘hot’ laboratories. SCK•CEN comprises three scientific institutes, i.e., the Institute of Nuclear Materials Science (NMS), the Institute of Advanced Nuclear Systems (ANS), and the Institute for Environment, Health and Safety (EHS). In particular, NMS carries out research on materials and fuels used both in present and future nuclear reactor systems. SCK•CEN has a long-standing experience in participating and/or coordinating projects funded by the European Commission. SCK•CEN boasts a range of unique set-ups for mechanical and corrosion tests in various environments (water, **heavy liquid metals**).

2.2.11.2 Staff involved

STAFF INVOLVED*	EXPERTISE/TASK	PERSON MONTHS
Erich STERGAR	Materials testing in HLM environments	2
Serguei GAVRILOV	Material testing in HLM environments	2
Marc VANKEERBERGHEN	Environmentally-assisted cracking R&D	8
Cholidah AKBAR FITRIANI	PhD student	6

*The first column should contain the name (preferred) or the qualification (e.g. technician). Indicate on this table if you expect to be able to recruit a PhD student or a post-doc.

2.2.11.3 Facilities used

NAME and/or CATEGORY*	USE IN THE PROJECT
Limets1	Electromechanic test machine for SSRT and fracture toughness testing in inert or LBE environment with oxygen concentration monitoring.
Limets4	Electromechanic test machine for SSRT and fracture toughness testing in inert or LBE environment with oxygen concentration monitoring.
Tensile test machine	Servo hydraulic tensile test machine for tensile, fracture toughness and pre-cracking in reference (air) environment and temperatures.
Corrosion autoclaves	Installations allowing for corrosion tests in lead or LBE up to temperatures of about 500 °C under controlled oxygen conditions.

*If the facility has a name, write it; in any case provide short description of it (e.g., Pb loop, hot cell lab, ion accelerator, ...)

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3.1 Publications

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3.2. EURATOM project deliverables

3.2.1. MATTER (2011 – 2015)

- D2.3 Slow Strain Rate Test round robin exercise.
- D3.2 Guidelines for fracture toughness testing in LBE.
- D3.4 Guidelines and results of Corrosion in liquid metals.
- D3.5 Guidelines, results and evaluations for fracture toughness tests.
- D3.6 Corrosion of T91 and 15-15Ti in LBE.
- D4.2 MATTER data sets hosted at MatDB.
- D4.7 Application of Codes to be LBE Environment.
- D9.1 The relevance of MATTER results for the Design of the ESNII reactors.
- D9.2 Materials Properties and selection.
- D9.3 Design Rules for Heavy Liquid Metal Cooled Fast Reactors.

3.2.2. MATTISSE (2013 – 2017)

- D5.41 Summary report of existing observations of LME on ferritic/martensitic steels.
- D5.42 Report for mechanical/microstructural Characterization of environmental assisted degradation effects of steels in lead alloys and assessment of environmental degradation effects on the performance of structural and functional components of MYRRHA ADS & LFR.

3.2.3. GEMMA (2017 – 2021)

- D2.8: Proposal for Material Design Curves relevant to HLM conditions.
- D2.9: Proposal for Design Rules and Assessment procedures on the incorporation of environmental effects to RCC-MRx, and related to welds.
- D4.2: Assessment of liquid metal corrosion for candidate materials and welds of LFR reactor.
- D4.6: Effect of liquid LBE on mechanical properties of austenitic steels, their welds and implications for design.
- D4.7: Effect of liquid lead on mechanical properties of austenitic steels, their welds and implications for design.
- D6.1: Data Management Plan.

4. Management and dissemination

4.1 Management

- Project coordinator (PC) and work package leaders (WPLs)
- Executive committee (ExCom)
 - Work package leaders and project coordinator
 - Sets goals, tracks progress, resolves issues, etc.
 - Convenes monthly, online (MS-Teams), if needed
- Management platform
 - CIRCABC hosted by JRC
 - Sections for ExCom, WP1-5, meetings, etc.
 - Accessible to all partners

4.2 Planned meetings

- Physical (if travel is feasible) hosted by WPL organisations
 - Kick-off meeting; hosted by SCK CEN or JRC
 - Three, yearly project meetings (November/December); hosted by JRC or SCK CEN, KIT and CVR
 - Closing workshop; host to be decided
- Online meetings
 - 2 online project meetings per year (March/April & August/September)
 - Ad-hoc online work package meetings as required
 - Monthly ExCom meeting, if required

4.3 List of milestones

WP1

- M1.1: Material data identified (month 12)
- M1.2: Repository ready (month 12)
- M1.3: Repository filled out with existing data (month 18)

WP2

- M2.1: DOE approaches reviewed (month 12)
- M2.2: Statistical techniques for material data evaluation reviewed (month 18)

WP3

- M3.1: Preferred DOE and statistical analysis applied (month 24)
- M3.2: Gap assessment 1: Suggestion for complementary testing (month 24)
- M3.3: Completeness and quality rating given (month 24)
- M3.4: Dependencies evaluated (month 36)
- M3.5: Gaps assessment 2: Future test programmes (month 36)

WP4

- M4.1: Complementary test data generated (month 36)
- M4.2: Complementary test data rated (month 42)

WP5

- M5.1: Recommendations drafted (month 42)

